

1 **DESIGN OF OPTIMAL WINE DISTILLATION RECIPES USING**
2 **MULTICRITERIA DECISION MAKING TECHNIQUES**

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18 **ABSTRACT**

19 In this work, dynamic multi-objective optimization and multicriteria decision making
20 (MCDM) techniques were applied to design recipes for optimal alembic wine distillations.
21 The optimization problem considered eight objectives associated with sensorial quality,
22 food safety, productivity and efficiency. Through correlation analysis of the optimal
23 solutions, it was possible to reduce the original objectives into four conflicting objectives.
24 Seven MCDM methods were tested to select the best recipes considering five scenarios. In
25 the equal priority scenario, each multi-criterion decision-making algorithm selected
26 different solutions. In scenarios with higher priority for a single objective, most multi-
27 criteria decision-making algorithms selected similar or identical solutions. A well balanced
28 performance was achieved when a high priority was assigned to ethanol recovery. The
29 methodology of this work can be easily adapted to define recipes for the optimal operation
30 of any fruit batch distillation process.

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32 **Keywords:** dynamic multi-objective optimization; multicriteria decision making; weighted
33 cost function; batch distillation; distillation recipes; spirits.

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38 1 INTRODUCTION

39 The spirits industry faces an increasingly competitive market, driving companies to develop
40 new products. Traditionally, the art of the distillation of spirits is to balance productivity
41 and distinctive flavor, ensuring a product free from off-flavors and toxic compounds
42 (López et al., 2017); however, now cost and environmental impact are important factors to
43 consider for the sustainability of the business. The most important operating variables
44 during the batch distillation of spirits are the head, heart and tail cut volumes, as well as the
45 heating power and reflux rate policies (R. Luna et al., 2018; Luna et al., 2019; Osorio et al.,
46 2005). In turn, operating variables in spirit distillations can be defined: to achieve a given
47 ethanol recovery, track a specified alcoholic strength of the distillate (Spaho et al., 2013) or
48 track a predefined condenser inlet temperature (Spaho, 2017). In the industry, experienced
49 operators through tasting and smelling usually define the operating variables, until the
50 desired product is obtained; hence, developing new products is slow and expensive
51 (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Bencomo et al., 2016). It is extremely hard to design
52 spirit distillation recipes that are able to effectively balance all of the aforementioned
53 performance criteria, based solely on the decision of experienced distillers.

54 The model-based approach to design operating strategies for spirit batch distillations (R.
55 Luna et al., 2018; Luna et al., 2019; Osorio et al., 2005) is cheaper and more reproducible
56 than the tasting and smelling approach (Sacher et al., 2017). The optimal distillation recipes
57 can be designed with a suitable model and applying standard optimization techniques.
58 Batch distillation models are described by a set of nonlinear differential and algebraic
59 equations (DAEs). Several spirit distillation models have been reported in the literature for
60 plate columns (Osorio et al., 2005, 2004), packed columns (Carvallo et al., 2011) and

61 copper Charentais alembics (Luna et al., 2019, 2018; Sacher et al., 2013; Scanavini et al.,
62 2012, 2010; Soares et al., 2019). Osorio et al. (2005) and De Lucca et al. (2013) found
63 optimal reflux rate paths for batch distillation columns to enhance the aroma and safety of
64 Muscat wine distillates (pisco).

65 The distillation of spirits involves many objectives that must be optimized simultaneously,
66 although most of the time, these objectives are conflicting, i.e., achieving an improvement
67 in one objective leads to a deterioration in another one. These recipes are better designed
68 within a multi-objective optimization (MOO) framework. The solution of a MOO problem
69 is a set of optimal points known as non-dominated solutions or Pareto front (PF), and their
70 optimal decision variables are known as the Pareto set. There are several strategies reported
71 in the literature to generate the Pareto front, where the scalarization based approach is the
72 most used since it is simple to implement (Bhaskar et al., 2000; Miettinen and Hakanen,
73 2009). In this approach, the MOO problem is turned into a traditional single-objective
74 problem, yielding a single optimal point of the Pareto front per optimization run. The
75 weighting method and the epsilon constraint method are widely used scalarization
76 algorithms. Luna et al. (2018) used the weighting method to find optimal operating
77 strategies for Charentais alembic spirit distillations. They identified a trade-off between
78 ethanol recovery maximization and methanol content minimization. Moreover, using the
79 same approach, Luna et al. (2019) found that the minimization of head-cut markers
80 conflicts with both maximization of heart-cut markers and minimization of tail-cut markers.
81 Even though scalarization methods are quite useful, they yield sparse Pareto fronts, and
82 present difficulties with non-convex or discontinuous optimization problems (Thibault,
83 2017).

84 Multi-objective evolutionary algorithms (MOEA) have been developed and successfully
85 applied in many engineering applications (Bhaskar et al., 2000; Sharma and Rangaiah,
86 2013; Zaman and Rangaiah, 2017). The most commonly used and well-known MOEA is
87 NSGA-II (Deb et al., 2002). MOEA algorithms apply the Pareto dominance concept to
88 yield many optimal points in the Pareto front in one optimization run, and hence they are
89 more efficient than traditional methods. Multi-objective Bayesian optimization algorithms
90 are also a good option, particularly the TS-EMO (Thompson Sampling Efficient Multi-
91 objective) algorithm (Bradford et al., 2018; Schweidtmann, 2020). This algorithm has
92 shown improved performance compared to NSGA-II on a set of test functions (Bradford et
93 al., 2018) and has been applied to develop a computer aided design system for continuous
94 flow reactor arrangements (Schweidtmann et al., 2018). Soares et al. (2019) solved a
95 dynamic MOO for parameter estimations of a batch cachaça distillation model in a copper
96 alembic. The multi-objective optimization was solved with a particle swarm (MOPSO)
97 algorithm and the optimal solution (fitted parameters) was selected manually.

98 Choosing a particular solution from a high dimension Pareto front is challenging (Lemos et
99 al., 2018); this is called multicriteria decision making (MCDM). Several MCDM
100 techniques have been developed based on heuristic procedures and parameters that must be
101 defined by the decision-maker. Wang and Rangaiah (2017) compared 10 methods for
102 selecting an optimal solution from the Pareto front in 13 chemical engineering problems.
103 Considering criteria such as user inputs, simplicity, and applicability, they found that the
104 best methods are: the technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution
105 (TOPSIS), gray relational analysis (GRA) and simple additive weighting (SAW).

106 In recent years, MOEAs and MCDM techniques have been used in the optimization of
107 batch distillations, which is a challenging multi-objective dynamic optimization problem.
108 This kind of problem looks for optimal operating conditions such as boiler heating power
109 and reflux rate paths, and optimal design variables like the number of trays (Parhi et al.,
110 2019a, 2019b, 2020; Reddy et al., 2017). However, the design of optimal recipes for spirit
111 distillations has not been tackled yet using MOEA and MCDM methods. In addition, most
112 of previous studies in this area consider few objectives.

113 In this paper, we solved a multi-objective dynamic optimization problem using the TS-
114 EMO algorithm (Bradford et al., 2018) to find a set of optimal operation recipes for Muscat
115 wine distillations. The decision variables were the heating power path, the head-cut
116 volume, and the heart-cut volume. We consider here many more objectives than previous
117 studies in this area, rendering the optimization and decision making problems more
118 challenging. The objectives included are productivity (ethanol recovery), efficiency (energy
119 consumption), as well as spirits' aromatic quality and safety (acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate,
120 methanol, linalool, hexanoic acid, and β -phenylethanol). Then, we applied seven simple
121 MCDM techniques to select optimal distillation recipes. Finally, we compare the selected
122 optimal solutions of MCDM algorithms with the solutions obtained with the multi-
123 objective weighting approach.

124 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

125 **2.1 Process model**

126 The multi-component alembic distillation model developed and validated by Luna et al.
127 (2019) is used to apply the Bayesian optimization algorithm and the multicriteria decision-

128 making techniques. This model simulates lab-scale distillations carried out on an automatic
129 Charentais copper alembic. The model is described by a differential-algebraic equation
130 system (DAEs) that includes i) total mass, component and energy dynamic balances in the
131 boiler, and ii) total mass, component and energy pseudo-stationary balances in the partial
132 condenser. The DAE system comprises 16 differential equations, 46 explicit algebraic
133 equations and one implicit algebraic equation (Luna et al., 2019). The model includes two
134 inputs: electric heating power (manipulated variable) and room temperature (disturbance).
135 The model outputs are the head temperature of the alembic (controlled variable), the
136 distillate volume, the alcohol strength in the distillate and the congener concentrations in
137 the distillate (Figure 1), specifically acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate, methanol, linalool,
138 hexanoic acid, and β -phenylethanol. The activity coefficients for each congener were
139 estimated using the UNIFAC group contribution method. The initial conditions of the
140 DAEs correspond to the Muscat wine used in Luna et al. (2019): 95 moles of wine, 0.038
141 ethanol molar fraction, $7.16e-05$ acetaldehyde molar fraction, $5.39e-05$ methanol molar
142 fraction, $1.55e-05$ ethyl acetate molar fraction, $1.27e-07$ linalool molar fraction, $1.34e-06$
143 hexanoic acid molar fraction and $5.00e-06$ β -phenylethanol molar fraction.

144 **2.2 Multi-objective dynamic optimization**

145 The multi-objective cost function considers product quality and safety, as well as process
146 efficiency and productivity. Quality and safety are associated with the congener's
147 composition in the heart-cut, i.e., low concentrations of head and tail markers (off-flavors
148 or toxic compounds), as well as high concentrations of heart markers (fruity and floral
149 aromas). Productivity is given by the ethanol recovery in the heart-cut, while process
150 efficiency is defined by the energy consumption (due to boiler heating).

151 The multi-objective optimization problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Min } F(x_i) = [f_1(x_i), f_2(x_i), \dots, f_n(x_i)] \quad (1)$$

152 Subject to,

$$\frac{dy_n}{dt} = z(y_n, x_i, t), n = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

$$g_j(x_i) \geq 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, J$$

$$h_k(x_i) = 0, k = 1, 2, \dots, K$$

$$x_i^L \leq x_i \leq x_i^U, i = 1, 2, \dots, I$$

153 where $f(x_i)$ represents the objectives that must be minimized simultaneously, $z(y_n, x_i, t)$
154 represents the differential equations of the model, $g(x_i)$ represents the inequality
155 constraints, $h(x_i)$ represents the equality constraints, and x_i the decision variables. Table 1
156 summarizes all the objectives, their descriptions and type of objective, i.e., if they are
157 maximized or minimized. The decision variables were the heating power path, as well as
158 the head-cut and heart-cut volumes. The optimization constraints were defined by
159 experience: 250-450 W for the heating power path, 40-200 mL for the head-cut volume,
160 and 200-500 mL for the heart-cut volume. The heating power path was discretized into 10
161 equally spaced time intervals; the first four correspond to the head and the last six to the
162 heart (Luna et al., 2019). The resulting MOO contains 12 optimization variables, 63

163 equality constraints, and 12 inequality constraints (upper and lower bounds of decision
164 variables). The optimization problem was solved within MATLAB R2015a using the TS-
165 EMO algorithm available at GitHub (Schweidtmann, 2020). The parameters of the
166 algorithms such as the maximum number of function evaluations, population size, number
167 of generations, and total number of iterations were defined equal to 100.

168 **2.2 Definitive selection of objectives and reduction of MOO by correlation analysis**

169 Figure 2 shows the Pareto front of the eight objectives for the optimal distillation recipes.
170 Acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate (head-markers) were negatively correlated with the other
171 objectives (conflicting objectives), but they were highly correlated among themselves
172 ($R > 0.95$) (harmonic objectives). Therefore, only one head-marker is needed in the objective
173 cost function. Maximization of the heart-marker (linalool) is harmonic with minimization
174 of the tail markers and with minimization of the energy consumption. Figure 2 shows
175 positive correlation of linalool with methanol ($R = 0.91$), hexanoic acid ($R = 0.81$), β -
176 phenylethanol ($R = 0.86$) and energy consumption ($R = 0.87$). Linalool is the most
177 characteristic aroma of young Muscat wine spirits; hence, we decided to include it in the
178 cost function.

179 Minimization of tail-markers (methanol, hexanoic acid and β -phenylethanol) are harmonic
180 among them and they show negative correlation with head-markers (acetaldehyde and ethyl
181 acetate), low positive correlation with linalool ($R < 0.95$), no correlation with ethanol, and
182 high positive correlation with energy ($R > 0.95$). Consequently, only one of these tail-
183 markers was included in the multi-objective cost function. Finally, ethanol recovery was
184 not correlated with any objective, and therefore must be included in the cost function.

185 It is worthwhile noting that the MOO framework here shows a novel perspective of the
186 optimal process operation space. Correlations between all the objectives under optimal
187 conditions can be easily found; hence, the optimal operation space can be reduced to a few
188 conflicting response variables. For alembic distillations, we propose four objectives: i)
189 minimization of acetaldehyde concentration in the heart-cut (low quality index), ii)
190 maximization of linalool concentration in the heart-cut (high quality index), iii)
191 maximization of ethanol recovery (productivity index), and iv) minimization of energy
192 consumption (efficiency index). Figure 3 shows that, after solving the reduced MOO
193 problem, the selected objectives are conflicting or poorly correlated with each other.
194 Therefore, it seems reasonable to apply MCDM algorithms to choose optimal distillation
195 recipes from this Pareto set. This reduction objectives approach for MOO is simpler and
196 more intuitive, although less rigorous than the one proposed by Gonzalez-Garay and
197 Guillen-Gosalbez (2018); they proposed a preliminary optimization for each objective
198 separately. Then, some objectives are removed iteratively, and the Pareto dominance
199 between solutions are checked in the reduced space. An error index was calculated between
200 the Pareto front of full-space and the reduced space. The algorithm stops when a maximum
201 number of objectives have been removed while maintaining the error below a given
202 tolerance.

203 **2.3 Selection of optimal distillation recipe by MCDM algorithms**

204 The solution of the MOO problem is an objective matrix f with m rows for each optimal
205 solution and n columns for each objective. Here, each optimal solution corresponds to a
206 distillation recipe that optimized simultaneously the conflicting objectives (see section 2.2).
207 Then, seven simple MCDM algorithms were applied to select an optimal solution: TOPSIS,

208 LINMAP, VIKOR, SAW, MEW, GRA and FUCA (Wang and Rangaiah, 2017). Each
 209 MCDM algorithms involve different mathematical procedures to select a Pareto-optimal
 210 solution (equations are available in the supplementary information). These algorithms
 211 require as input the objective matrix f and the weight for each objective w_j defined by the
 212 user. To evaluate different kinds of Muscat spirits that can be produced in a distillery, five
 213 scenarios with different weights, w_j , for each objective were defined: (C1) equal priority,
 214 (C2) acetaldehyde priority, (C3) linalool priority, (C4) ethanol recovery priority and (C5)
 215 energy consumption priority. Table 2 shows the values of the weights for each case.

216 Particularly, the VIKOR algorithm requires an additional decision-making parameter γ that
 217 was fixed equal to 0.5 (see supplementary information). In addition, the GRA algorithm
 218 does not include weights; hence, the selected solution will be the same in all scenarios.

219 **2.4 Multi-objective weighting function**

220 To compare the performance of MOO and MCDM algorithms, a multi-objective cost
 221 function with the conflictive objectives (see section 2.2) based on the weighting method
 222 (W-method) was defined:

$$Min J = w_1 \cdot \frac{C_{acet}(t_f)}{100} - w_2 \cdot \frac{C_{lin}(t_f)}{2} - w_3 \cdot \frac{Rec_{eth}(t_f)}{100} + w_4 \cdot \int_0^{t_f} \frac{Q_{cal}(t) \cdot dt}{1000} \quad (2)$$

223 where, w_1 , w_2 , w_3 and w_4 correspond to the relative weights for each objective. Like in
 224 Luna et al. (2019), each objective was scaled by its maximum value. The weights were set
 225 using the same combinations defined for the MCDM algorithms (Table 2). Therefore, five

226 optimization problems were solved using a scatter search metaheuristic code (Egea et al.,
227 2007), with 1000 maximum number of function evaluations and *fminsearch* as local solver.

228 **3 RESULTS**

229 **3.1 Equal priority for all objectives**

230 Figure 4 shows the Pareto front of all the objective pairs and the optimal solutions selected
231 by the seven MCDM algorithms and the W-method solution, giving equal weight to the
232 four objectives (see Table 2). The solutions selected by SAW and GRA methods were
233 practically the same (blue right-pointing triangle and green 5 points star in Figure 4,
234 respectively); their head and heart volumes were at the lower bounds (40 and 200 mL,
235 respectively), although their heating paths differed considerably (Figure 5). The solutions
236 chosen by TOPSIS and LINMAP (red circle and orange diamond in Figure 4, respectively)
237 were close since they are quite similar algorithms (Wang and Rangaiah, 2017). In this case,
238 the volume cuts were similar (head volume: 89.4 mL vs 85.2 mL, heart volume: 202 mL vs
239 219 mL), and the heating paths were different (Figure 5). The VIKOR solutions (yellow
240 upward-pointing triangle and greenish-yellow downward-pointing triangle) were also close,
241 with head volumes near the lower bound and similar heart volumes (301 and 319 mL); their
242 heating power paths were different though (Figure 5). The FUCA algorithm suggested an
243 optimal solution (purple 6 points star in Figure 4) that was closer to the VIKOR solutions
244 than to those suggested by the other algorithms. In this case, the head volume and heart
245 volume cuts were 60.9 and 288 mL, respectively. The MEW algorithm has chosen the most
246 different solution (light blue left-pointing triangle) with the largest head volume (185 mL).
247 The W-method solution (red cross) differed considerably from the solutions of the MCDM
248 algorithms: the heating power path was different, and the head volume and heart volume

249 cuts were 66.9 and 351.7 mL, respectively. Figure 6 compares each objective
250 (acetaldehyde, linalool, ethanol recovery, and energy consumption) for the optimal
251 solutions selected by the seven MCDM methods and W-method solution. MEW has chosen
252 the most different solution, characterized by a high rectification (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016);
253 consequently, energy consumption was high, and recoveries of congeners and ethanol were
254 low. This is not a good option since it will yield an expensive and aromatically neutral
255 spirit. The rest of the selected optimal solutions present ethanol recoveries normally
256 observed in commercial wine distillations (between 40 and 72%) (Léauté, 1990) and low
257 energy consumptions (300-500 Wh). However, these solutions yielded extremely different
258 linalool and acetaldehyde recoveries, covering the whole attainability range. TOPSIS and
259 LINMAP solutions stand out for showing relatively low acetaldehyde concentrations
260 without significant linalool losses. Since MCDM algorithms have chosen quite different
261 solutions in this case, it is advisable to select at least two MCDM solutions to test
262 experimentally. Most recipes yielded spirits that exceeded the acetaldehyde odor threshold
263 of 25 g/hL.a.a. (Christoph and Bauer-Christoph (2007), providing positive notes such as
264 sweetish cut apple or nut (Apostolopoulou et al., 2005). However, these values were below
265 the maximum acetaldehyde relative concentration (100 g/hL.a.a.) allowed by the Chilean
266 law (Biblioteca del congreso nacional de Chile and Ministerio de Agricultura, 2020). The
267 SAW and GRA solutions were an exception, yielding toxic and low quality spirits (Cortés
268 et al., 2005; Silva et al., 2000). Additionally, there is an important odor-interactive effect
269 between acetaldehyde and other spirit compounds that can influence the fruity perception
270 (Matias-Guiu et al., 2018a). The VIKOR method selected the best recipe of the equal
271 priority scenario, characterized by higher ethanol recoveries (70%) than those observed in

272 the production of cognac and fruit brandies (55%-60%) (García-Llobodanin et al., 2011;
273 Léauté, 1990), as well as high linalool concentrations and medium energy consumptions.
274 These types of recipes will be useful to elaborate young spirits without aging, characterized
275 by a terpenic character; hence, preserving better the quality of the raw material. In addition,
276 the relation between quality and production is favorable, since these recipes are
277 characterized by moderate levels of acetaldehyde, relatively low energy consumption, and
278 acceptable productivity.

279 **3.2 Different priorities for each objective**

280 As expected, for the acetaldehyde minimization priority case, all algorithms selected
281 solutions that prioritize the reduction of acetaldehyde (Figure S1). The GRA algorithm was
282 an exception since it does not require any weight, yielding only one solution in all
283 scenarios. TOPSIS and LINMAP selected identical solutions (Figure S2). According to
284 Wang and Rangaiah (2017), the algorithms TOPSIS and LINMAP usually recommended
285 similar solutions or sometimes exactly the same solution. SAW and MEW correspond to a
286 similar MCDM approach, so therefore they also proposed identical solutions. As seen in the
287 equal priority case, the VIKOR methods choose two similar solutions, while FUCA
288 selected a solution with a heart-cut volume close to the lower bound (Figure S2). Moreover,
289 the W-method solution was similar to the optimal solutions selected by TOPSIS, LINMAP
290 and FUCA. Overall, all these optimal solutions are characterized by large head volumes
291 (Figure S2), low linalool concentrations and low ethanol recoveries (less than 50%) (Figure
292 S3). These is in accordance with previous studies (Luna et al., 2019; Matias-Guiu et al.,
293 2018b), i.e., to reduce acetaldehyde (head-marker) content in the heart-cut, large head-cut
294 volume are required, reducing the concentration of linalool and increasing the concentration

295 of tail compound in the heart-cut (longer distillation times). The spirits obtained through
296 these types of recipes are characterized by low aromatic quality and low economic
297 performance, thus they are not a good option for comercial distilleries.

298 In contrast, the recipes obtained for equal priority for all objectives (section 3.1) are more
299 interesting to apply in the industry, showing a good economic performance since the
300 productivity was high and the energy cost moderate; moreover, the achieved acetaldehyde
301 concentrations were below the legal limit.

302 When linalool maximization is the priority, all MCDM methods (including W-method)
303 selected similar or identical solutions, (Figure S4), characterized by extremely small head
304 and heart volumes (in the lower bounds or close to them). Here, the decision variables of
305 the solution selected by GRA were exactly those of the SAW, MEW, FUCA, and VIKOR-1
306 solutions (Figure S5). Even though TOPSIP, LINMAP, VIKOR-2 and W-method optimal
307 operations applied different heating paths than those of the other algorithms, in the end they
308 yield similar performance (Figure S4). These solutions reinforced previous analysis in Luna
309 et al. (2019) that volume cuts are more determinant than the heating path in the optimal
310 operation of alembics (Figure S5). Overall, these distillation recipes were characterized by
311 high linalool contents, yielding a high aromatic quality spirit. However, all these recipes
312 yielded acetaldehyde concentrations higher than that permitted by the Chilean law (100
313 g/hL.a.a.) (Biblioteca del congreso nacional de Chile and Ministerio de Agricultura, 2020).
314 Even though the energy consumption of these recipes were low, productivities were low
315 also (Figure S6). Therefore, these alternatives are not an attractive option to apply in the
316 industry as compared to the case of equal priority for all objectives.

317 In the scenario of high ethanol priority, all MCDM methods selected similar or identical
318 solutions (including W-method), with the exception of GRA (Figure S7). Here, the decision
319 variables of the VIKOR-1 solution were identical to those of SAW and FUCA (Figure S8).
320 All ethanol priority solutions defined small head-cut volumes (close or equal to the lower
321 bound) and large heart-cut volumes (close or equal to the upper bound 500 mL) (Figure
322 S8). As expected, in these solutions ethanol recoveries were high (around 85%), although
323 their heart-cuts contained moderate amounts of acetaldehyde (around 75 g/hL.a.a.),
324 moderate amounts of linalool (around 0.7 g/hL.a.a.) and consumed a moderate amount of
325 energy (450 W-h) (Figure S9). These types of recipes should be preferred for producing
326 aged spirits, since terpenic compounds are not as relevant as wood descriptors in the spirit's
327 quality. In addition, the high ethanol yield and the moderate energy cost would allow to
328 obtain economically competitive products.

329 When energy consumption was the priority (Figure S10), the decision variables defined by
330 SAW, MEW, FUCA, and VIKOR-1 were exactly the same (Figure S11). Meanwhile, the
331 VIKOR-2 operating variables coincided with those of the GRA algorithm (Figure S11).
332 Here, the W-method solution was similar to the MCDM solutions; the heating power path
333 was different, but the head and heart volumes were practically the same (44.6 and 200 mL,
334 respectively). These energy priority distillations defined the head-cut and heart-cut volumes
335 at the lower limit, except for TOPSIS and LINMAP that defined higher head volumes (59.9
336 and 63.4 mL, respectively). Even though some of these recipes defined different heating
337 paths, they all achieved high linalool contents in the heart-cut (Figure S12). These
338 distillates were characterized by ethanol recoveries close to 50% and high acetaldehyde
339 contents in the heart-cut (higher than the legal limit 100 g/hL.a.a.), except TOPSIS and

340 LINMAP solutions. Finally, as expected, energy consumptions were extremely low (lower
341 than 210 Wh) (Figure S12). These recipes are not a good option to produce neither young
342 spirits nor aged spirits.

343 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

344 A multi-objective optimization framework considerably facilitates the design of new
345 optimal alembic distillation recipes that simultaneously improve the quality and safety of
346 the product as well as the process efficiency and productivity. It was verified that TS-EMO
347 is an efficient algorithm to solve MOO dynamic distillation problems with up to eight
348 objectives. Analyzing the correlations of the solutions in the Pareto front after solving the
349 original eight objectives MOO, it was possible to define an equivalent MOO problem with
350 only four objectives. Therefore, the MOO framework demonstrated that it is a powerful
351 tool for designing spirit distillation processes; it also showed a novel perspective of the
352 optimal operation space, reducing the multiple criteria of the distillation process. Seven
353 MCDM techniques were assessed for selecting optimal operating recipes from the Pareto
354 front, considering different priorities. In addition, we compared these selected optimal
355 solutions with a traditional approach to solve a multi-objective optimization like W-
356 method. When all the objectives were given equal priority, the MCDM algorithms and W-
357 method suggested quite different solutions. Hence, in this case at least two MCDM
358 solutions should be analyzed further before real time implementation. Here, the VIKOR
359 method stood out among the MCDM methods selecting the best recipe characterized by
360 high ethanol recoveries, high linalool content, and medium energy consumptions. This is
361 the most convenient recipe to produce young spirits. In turn, when specific objectives were
362 given priority, most of the time the MCDM algorithms and the W-method selected similar

363 or identical solutions. Therefore, in these cases only one MCDM method will suffice to
364 choose an optimal operation recipe for real time implementation. When ethanol recovery
365 was given priority, a balanced performance was achieved, where ethanol recovery was high
366 (85%) and the rest of the objective values were found in the middle of their attainable
367 range. These recipes should be applied to produce aged spirits. Overall, Bayesian
368 algorithms like TS-EMO are computationally more efficient than the W-method using a
369 global optimization solver. One optimization run of TS-EMO obtain many Pareto solutions,
370 while the W-method obtain only one Pareto solution per run. Nevertheless, the solutions
371 obtained by the W-method were similar to the optimal solutions selected by the MCDM
372 techniques that we tested. The optimization procedure described here can be applied to any
373 spirit alembic distillation and easily extended to any spirit production process using
374 different distillation equipment.

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377

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487

488 **Figure Captions**

489 **Figure 1.** Process diagram of the Charentais alembic distillation system.

490 **Figure 2.** Correlation analysis among pairs of the eight distillation objectives.

491 **Figure 3.** Correlation analysis among pairs for the reduction of MOO problem into four
492 distillation objectives.

493 **Figure 4.** Pareto front for all objective pairs, optimal solutions selected by MCDM
494 algorithms and weighting method solution for equal priority in all objectives.

495 **Figure 5.** Optimal distillation recipes selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and
496 weighting method solution for equal priority in all objectives. Red dashed line
497 indicates the division between head and heart fraction periods. Red and blue bars
498 correspond to head and heart volumes, respectively.

499 **Figure 6.** Comparison of objectives performance selected by the seven MCDM algorithms
500 and weighting method solution for equal priority in all objectives.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix

Table 1. List of objectives considered for MOO in Muscat wine distillations.

	Objectives	Variable ^a	Description
1	Acetaldehyde	$C_{acet}(t_f)$	Head marker/toxic compound
2	Ethyl acetate	$C_{ea}(t_f)$	Head marker/off-flavor
3	Methanol	$C_{meth}(t_f)$	Tail marker/toxic compound
4	Linalool	$-C_{lin}(t_f)$	Heart marker/floral aroma
5	Hexanoic acid	$C_{hx}(t_f)$	Tail marker/off-flavor
6	β -phenylethanol	$C_{\beta-feOH}(t_f)$	Tail marker/roses aroma
7	Ethanol recovery	$-Rec_{eth}(t_f)$	Productivity
8	Energy consumption	$\int_0^{t_f} Q_{cal}(t) \cdot dt$	Efficiency

^a Positive sign indicates a minimization criterion and negative sign indicates a maximization criterion.

Table 2. Values of the weights considered in five scenarios for selecting an optimal distillation recipe.

Relative weight		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Acetaldehyde	w_1	0.25	0.70	0.10	0.10	0.10
Linalool	w_2	0.25	0.10	0.70	0.10	0.10
Ethanol recovery	w_3	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.70	0.10
Energy consumption	w_4	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.70

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CRediT author statement

Ricardo Luna: Data Curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization. Francisco Lopez.: Validation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. J. Ricardo Pérez-Correa: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Validation

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**DESIGN OF OPTIMAL WINE DISTILLATION RECIPES USING
MULTICRITERIA DECISION MAKING TECHNIQUES**

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Figure S1. Pareto front for all objective pairs, optimal solutions selected by MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for acetaldehyde minimization priority.

Figure S2. Optimal distillation recipes selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for acetaldehyde minimization priority. Red dashed line indicates the division between head and heart fraction periods. Red and blue bars correspond to head and heart volumes, respectively.

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Figure S3. Comparison of objectives performance selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for acetaldehyde minimization priority.

Figure S4. Pareto front for all objective pairs, optimal solutions selected by MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for linalool maximization priority.

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Figure S5. Optimal distillation recipes selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for linalool maximization priority. Red dashed line indicates the division between head and heart fraction periods. Red and blue bars correspond to head and heart volumes, respectively.

Figure S6. Comparison of objectives performance selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for linalool maximization priority.

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Figure S7. Pareto front for all objective pairs, optimal solutions selected by MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for ethanol recovery maximization priority.

Figure S8. Optimal distillation recipes selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for ethanol recovery maximization priority. Red dashed line indicates the division between head and heart fraction periods. Red and blue bars correspond to head and heart volumes, respectively.

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Figure S9. Comparison of objectives performance selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for ethanol recovery maximization priority.

Figure S10. Pareto front for all objective pairs, optimal solutions selected by MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for energy consumption minimization priority.

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Figures S11. Optimal distillation recipes selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for energy consumption minimization priority. Red dashed line indicates the division between head and heart fraction periods. Red and blue bars correspond to head and heart volumes, respectively.

Figure S12. Comparison of objectives performance selected by the seven MCDM algorithms and weighting method solution for energy consumption minimization priority.

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Multicriteria decision-making algorithms

1) Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to the Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)

The main idea of this technique is to evaluate the performance of optimal alternatives through the similarity with the positive-ideal solution (Krohling and Pacheco, 2015). The positive-ideal solution is composed of the best values of each criteria in the objective matrix, whereas the negative-ideal solution consists of the worst values of each criteria in the objective matrix (Wang and Rangaiah, 2017). This technique chooses the optimal solution that is farthest from the negative-ideal solution and closest to the positive-ideal solution (Krohling and Pacheco, 2015), according to Euclidean distance (Triantaphyllou, 2000). The procedure can be summarized as follows,

Step 1. Calculate the normalized objectives matrix,

$$F_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m f_{ij}^2}} \quad (1)$$

Step 2. Calculate the weighted product of the matrix of objectives, multiplying each column by its weight w_j

$$v_{ij} = F_{ij} \cdot w_j \quad (2)$$

Step 3. Determine the positive-ideal solution A^+ and negative-ideal solution A^- as follows,

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$$A^+ = \{(Max_i(v_{ij})|j \in J), (Min_i(v_{ij})|j \in J'), i = 1, 2, 3 \dots m\} = \{v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_j^+, \dots, v_n^+\} \quad (3)$$

$$A^- = \{(Min_i(v_{ij})|j \in J), (Max_i(v_{ij})|j \in J'), i = 1, 2, 3 \dots m\} = \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_j^-, \dots, v_n^-\} \quad (4)$$

where J is the set of maximization criterion objectives and J' is the set of minimization criterion objectives. A^+ contains the best values of each objective, i.e., the highest value for maximization objectives and the smallest value for minimization objectives within the columns of the objective matrix. Conversely, A^- contains the worst values of each objective, which correspond to the smallest and highest value within the columns of the objective matrix for maximization and minimization, respectively.

Step 4. Calculate the Euclidean distance between each solution and the positive-ideal and negative-ideal solutions, respectively,

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (5)$$

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

Step 5. Calculate the relative distance to the negative-ideal solution of each optimal solution,

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$$C_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^- + S_i^+} \quad (7)$$

The solution i with the highest value of C_i is the optimal solution selected. Hence, the smaller the value of S_i^+ and the larger the value of S_i^- , the better.

2) *Linear Programming Technique for Multidimensional Analysis of Preference (LINMAP)*

LINMAP is similar to TOPSIS; the main difference is that LINMAP only considers the Euclidean distance to the positive ideal solution (Eqs 1-5). The optimal solution selected is that with the smallest S_i^+ .

3) *Viekriterijumsko Kompromisno Rangiranje (VIKOR)*

Like LINMAP, the VIKOR method selects the solution that is closest to the positive-ideal solution. However, it uses a different norm to measure distances and requires specifying a decision-making parameter γ (Mardani et al., 2016; Wang and Rangaiah, 2017). The procedure is as follows,

Step 1. Determine the best (F_j^+) and worst (F_j^-) values for the sets of maximization criterion objectives (J) and minimization criterion objectives (J'), respectively,

$$F_j^+ = \max (f_{i\dots m,j}), F_j^- = \min (f_{i\dots m,j}), j \in J \quad (8)$$

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$$F_j^+ = \min (f_{i\dots m,j}), F_j^- = \max (f_{i\dots m,j}), j \in J' \quad (9)$$

Step 2. Calculate the sum of weighted fractional distances of each solution from the best possible value, S_i (utility measure), and the maximum of weighted fractional distances, R_i (regret measure), (Mardani et al., 2016),

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \left(\frac{F_j^+ - f_{ij}}{F_j^+ - F_j^-} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$R_i = \max_{j \dots n} \left[\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \left(\frac{F_j^+ - f_{ij}}{F_j^+ - F_j^-} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

where w_j represents the user defined weight for each objective.

Step 3. Compute the value Q_i ,

$$Q_i = \gamma \cdot \left(\frac{S_i - S^+}{S^- - S^+} \right) + (1 - \gamma) \cdot \left(\frac{R_i - R^+}{R^- - R^+} \right) \quad (12)$$

where

$$S^+ = \max_{i \dots m} (S_i), S^- = \min_{i \dots m} (S_i), R^+ = \min_{i \dots m} (R_i), R^- = \max_{i \dots m} (R_i)$$

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The parameter γ is the weight of the strategy or “strategy coefficient” (Martínez-Morales et al., 2010; Vučijak et al., 2013). Values of $0.5 < \gamma \leq 1$ represent a decision-making that tries to satisfy most of the criteria, whereas values lower than 0.5 prioritize the minimization of the individual differences from the ideal solution (Vučijak et al., 2013). In this work, we used $\gamma = 0.5$ that represents a consensus value for both strategies.

Step 4. Rank the optimal solutions, sorting by the S , R and Q values in increasing order (order least to greatest).

Step 5. Propose as a compromising solution the alternative $A^{(1)}$ by measuring the minimum value of Q_i if the following two conditions are satisfied:

C1. Acceptable advantage: $Q(A^{(2)}) - Q(A^{(1)}) \geq 1/(m - 1)$, where $A^{(2)}$ is the optimal solution in the second position ranking list by Q , and m is the number of alternatives or optimal solutions.

C2. Acceptable stability in decision making: alternative $A^{(1)}$ must also be the best ranked by S or/and R .

When C1 is satisfied and C2 is not satisfied, the solutions $A^{(1)}$ y $A^{(2)}$ are both recommended, whereas C1 is not satisfied and C2 is satisfied, the solutions $A^{(1)}$, $A^{(2)}$, ..., $A^{(d)}$ are all recommended. Here, $A^{(d)}$ is determined by the relation $Q(A^{(d)}) - Q(A^{(1)}) < 1/(m - 1)$ for maximum d (the positions of these alternatives are measured by their “closeness”).

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4) *Simple Additive weighting (SAW)*

The solution i of the objective matrix is ranked by summing the product of each normalized objective j and their respective weight, w_j . The selected solution corresponds to the highest score (Wang and Rangaiah, 2017).

Step 1. Normalize the objective matrix for maximization and minimization criterion, respectively.

$$F_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\text{Max}(f_{i\dots m,j})} \quad (13)$$

$$F_{ij} = \frac{\text{Min}(f_{i\dots m,j})}{f_{ij}} \quad (14)$$

Step 2. Calculate the weighted product of the objective matrix by

$$v_{ij} = F_{ij} \cdot w_j \quad (15)$$

Step 3. Calculate the sum of weighted values of each optimal solution

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n v_{ij} \quad (16)$$

Step 4. The highest value of S_i correspond to the optimal solution selected.

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5) *Multiplicative Exponent Weighting (MEW)*

The solution i of the objective matrix is ranked by the product of the weighted exponent of each normalized objective j . The MEW algorithm normalizes the objective matrix the same way as the SAW algorithm (Eqs 13 and 14). The weighted exponent is calculated as follows:

$$v_{ij} = F_{ij}^{w_j} \quad (17)$$

The product of the weighted exponent of each optimal solution is

$$S_i = \prod_{j=1}^n v_{ij} \quad (18)$$

The solution i with highest value of S_i is the optimal solution selected.

6) *Gray Relational Analysis (GRA)*

This algorithm selects an optimal solution through a gray relational coefficient (GRC), which describes the similarity between each candidate network and the best reference network (Martínez-Morales et al., 2010; Wang and Rangaiah, 2017). The GRA method does not require weights or any other inputs from the user.

Step 1. normalize the objective matrix according to larger the better (maximization) and smaller the better (minimization),

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$$F_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij} - \min (f_{i\dots m,j})}{\max (f_{i\dots m,j}) - \min (f_{i\dots m,j})} \quad (19)$$

$$F_{ij} = \frac{\max (f_{i\dots m,j}) - f_{ij}}{\max (f_{i\dots m,j}) - \min (f_{i\dots m,j})} \quad (20)$$

Step 2. Calculate the reference network point

$$F_j^{max} = \max (F_{i\dots m,j}) \quad (21)$$

Step 3. Calculate the difference between reference network point and each optimal solution

$$\Delta F_{ij} = |F_j^{max} - F_{ij}| \quad (22)$$

Step 4. Calculate the *GRC* of each optimal solution *i*

$$GRC_i = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\min (\Delta F_{ij}) + \max (\Delta F_{ij})}{\Delta F_{ij} + \max (\Delta F_{ij})} \quad (23)$$

Step 5. The selected optimal solution corresponds to the highest value of *GRC_i*

7) *Faire Un Choix Adéquat (FUCA)*

This is a simple method based on individual rankings of the objectives (Morales-Mendoza et al., 2011).

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Step 1. Generate an increasing ranking for each objective where rank 1 is established for the best value, whereas rank m (number of all optimal solutions or alternatives) is established for the worst value. For the maximization criterion, the best value must be the largest value. Contrarily, for the minimization criterion, the best value must be the smallest value.

Step 2. For each solution, calculate a weighted sum for each optimal solution i

$$v_i = \sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} \cdot w_j) \quad (24)$$

where r_{ij} is the rank of solution i for the objective j and w_j represents the weights for each objective.

Step 3. The alternative with the smallest v_i is the optimal solution selected.

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